

Online Repository 2:

Rapid drug desensitisation: One-bag protocol for intravenously administered biologics

This infusion plan applies to biologics dissolved in 525 ml. Infusion sets are primed with drug solution.

(According to regulations, infusion bags of 500 ml solvent (saline or glucose) should contain at least 500 ml, but in reality most contain up to 525 ml)

Following parameters of 11 infusion steps are coded in high precision infusion pumps (Infusomat Space® Braun)

Infusion steps	Volume to infuse	Duration	Infusion rate	Percentage of a standard infusion rate†	Percentage of target dose each step	Cumulative percentage of target dose
	(ml)	(min)	(ml/h)	(%)	(%)	(%)
Step 1	0.7	15	2.8	0.5	0.1	0.1
Step 2	1.3	15	5.2	1	0.2	0.4
Step 3	2.6	15	10.4	2	0.5	0.9
Step 4	5.3	15	21.2	4	1.0	1.9
Step 5	10.5	15	42.0	8	2.0	3.9
Step 6	15.8	15	63.2	12	3.0	6.9
Step 7	21.0	15	84.0	16	4.0	10.9
Step 8	52.5	30	105.0	20	10.0	20.9
Step 9	57.8	30	115.6	22	11.0	31.9
Step 10	63.0	30	126.0	24	12.0	43.9
Step 11	294.7	135	131.0	25	56.1	100
Final flushing	When the infusion bag with drug solvent is emptied, the infusion set still contains drug solvent. A infusion bag containing only flushing fluid is connected to the infusion set and infusion step 11 should be completed (all 135 min.), before increasing the infusion rate to 300 ml/h for 10 min.					
Total infusion time	5 hours and 40 minutes, including final flushing					

† A standard infusion rate is 525 ml/h, corresponding to a standard infusion duration of 1 hour.